

VI VERNADSKY'S COSMOLOGICAL THEORY

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Abstract.

Analyzing the geological history of the Earth, Vernadsky points out that the process of the biosphere's transition to a new state, the nososphere, is taking place under the influence of a new geological force, the scientific thinking of mankind. However, in the works of Vernadsky, the essence of the material nosphere as a modified biosphere is not fully and consistently interpreted. In some cases, he wrote about the nosphere in the future, in others in the present, and sometimes he connected the formation of the nosphere with the appearance of a rational person or the emergence of industrial production. It should be noted that when Vernadsky wrote about the geological activity of man as a mineralogist, he did not yet use the concepts of "nosphere" and even "biosphere". He wrote about the appearance of the nosphere on Earth from the point of view of the history of science under the title "Planetary Phenomena of Scientific Thought".

Keywords.

Biosphere, Noosphere, geological activity, mineralogy, geological force, nitrogen, gas shell, oxygen, organism, invertebrates

INTRODUCTION

Currently, with the increasing impact of scientific and technical progress on the environment, it is connected with the aggravation of the planetary ecological situation, which threatens the continued existence of all living beings on earth, the scientific and public interests of the teaching of VI is digging. Vernadsky gave a lot of information about the biosphere in his fundamental works.

One of the greatest achievements of natural science: 20th century - Vernadsky's doctrine of the biosphere, the sphere of life that interacts with living organisms (living matter) and inert matter. Subject: this subject was first developed by teacher Vernadsky. VVDokuchaev also paid attention to the unity of the material and spiritual culture of people with the natural environment. But if Dokuchaev was primarily concerned with the practical aspects of this problem,

then Vernadsky tried to create a theoretically coherent concept of the transition of the biosphere to the nosphere as a result of logical results. Changed by science - the environment of life - by man. Vernadsky was born in Petersburg. The mother was Ukrainian and the founder of the family, Vernadsky came from Zaporizhzhya Sich. [1] A lifelong scholar, he maintained a love for the Ukrainian language, culture, history, and science. VIVernadsky gave an excellent education. He studied at St. Petersburg University in the 80s of the last century, when the great scientists VVDovzhenko, DIMendeleev, OIVoykov and OMBeketov taught there. MPWagner and others. His methodology was a different effective approach to human problems. He called and other scientists not only compare the scientific outlook of different eras, but also study the structure of science in harmony with other forms of social consciousness - philosophy, religion, art. Material practices and social conditions of the population. The thinker Lomonosov wrote excellent articles about Kant's work and quoted the world's most famous scientists in his scientific works. He considered the scientific method to be important, not the only way to know the truth. In this document, we will consider the concepts of living and inert matter that make up the biosphere, living, inert and biocos natural bodies by VIVernadsky. VIVernadsky's approach to the problem of the origin of life is considered. In the modern era, the concept of the transition of the biosphere to the nosphere is analyzed. [2]

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

Cosmological theory . For the first time, the term "biosphere" was introduced by the naturalist and thinker Jean Baptiste Lamarck (1744 - 1829). In 1875, the term "Biosphere" was introduced to science by the Australian geologist Edward Suess. He understood a thin film of life on earth by the biosphere. The role and importance of the biosphere for the development of life on our planet is so great that already in the first third of the 20th century. In natural science, a new fundamental scientific direction appeared - the doctrine of the biosphere, the founder of which was the great Russian scientist V.I. Vernadsky. The first basis for the existence of the biosphere and the biogeochemical processes occurring in it is the astronomical location of our planet and, first of all, its distance from the Sun and the approach of the earth's axis to the ecliptic or the plane of the earth's orbit. This spatial arrangement of the Earth mainly determines the climate on the planet, and the second, in turn, is the life cycle of all organisms that exist on it. The sun is the main source of energy for the biosphere and the controller of all geological, chemical and biological processes on our planet. One of the authors of the law expressed this role in a metaphorical sense. preservation and transformation of life

Julius Meyer (1814-1878), he emphasized the creation of the rays of the sun of life [3]. The Earth and its environment were formed as a result of the logical development of the entire Solar System. About 4.7 billion years ago, a protosolar planet formed from dust-scattering gas in the protosolar system. Like other planets, the Earth receives energy from the Sun and falls on the surface in the form of electromagnetic radiation.

Atmosphere. The gas shell consists mainly of nitrogen and oxygen. It contains small amounts of carbon dioxide (0.03%) and ozone. The state of the atmosphere has a great influence on the physical, chemical and biological processes that occur on the surface of the earth and in the water environment. Of great importance for biological processes: oxygen, which is used for respiration and mineralization of dead organic matter, carbon dioxide, which participates in photosynthesis, and ozone, which protects the earth's surface from strong ultraviolet radiation. Nitrogen, carbon dioxide, and water vapor are mainly formed as a result of volcanic activity and photosynthesis[4].

Hydrosphere. Water is the most important component of the biosphere and one of the necessary factors for the existence of living organisms. Its main part (95%) is in the oceans, which occupy 70% of the Earth's surface and contain 1300 million km³. Surface water (lakes, rivers) is only 0.182 million km³, and the amount of water in living organisms is only 0.001 million km³. Large reserves of water (24 million km³) include glaciers. Gases dissolved in water are of great importance: oxygen and carbon dioxide. Their number varies with temperature and the presence of living organisms. Carbon dioxide in water is 60 times more than in the atmosphere. The hydrosphere has been associated with the development of the lithosphere, which has released large amounts of water vapor throughout Earth's geologic history.[5]

Lithosphere. Most of the organisms that live inside the lithosphere are located in the soil layer, the depth of which does not exceed several meters. The composition of the soil includes mineral substances formed during the destruction of rocks and organic substances - products of the vital activity of organisms.

Living organisms (living matter) . Despite the narrow boundaries of the biosphere, living organisms within them are very unevenly distributed. At high altitudes and deep in the hydrosphere and lithosphere, organisms are relatively rare. Life is concentrated mainly on the surface of the Earth, in the soil and in the surface layer of the ocean. The total mass of living organisms is estimated at 2.43 * 10¹⁰ tons, 99.2% of the biomass of terrestrial organisms is provided by green plants, 0.8% by animals and microorganisms. In contrast, in the ocean, plants make up

6.3%, and animals and microorganisms make up 93.7% of the biomass. Life is mainly on land. The total ocean biomass is only 0.03×10 tons, or 0.13% of all life on Earth.

An important pattern is observed in the distribution of living organisms by species composition. 21% of the total number of species are plants, but their share in the total biomass is 99%). Among animals, 96% of species are invertebrates and only 4% are vertebrates, one tenth of which are mammals. The mass of living matter is only 0.01-0.02% of the inert matter of the biosphere, but it plays a leading role in geochemical processes. The body receives substances and energy necessary for metabolism from the external environment. A limited amount of living matter regenerates, changes and decomposes. Every year, about 10%) of the biomass increases due to the vital activity of plants and animals. V. I. Vernadsky of education _ essence of the planet appearance o ' which changes " alive of matter " absolutely importance admit from getting consists of The sun warm up Earth climate main structural from the parts one to be , to be many _ geological of processes development for is the basis . A large flow of heat comes from the depths of the earth. Our planet has a different structure and consists of concentric shells (geospheres) - inner and outer. The core includes the core, mantle and the outer - lithosphere, hydrosphere, atmosphere and complex shell of the Earth's biosphere. The boundaries of the biosphere are determined by the factors of the earth's environment that make the existence of living organisms impossible. The upper boundary passes 20 km above the surface of the planet and is bounded by the ozone layer, which delays the short-wave part of the sun's ultraviolet radiation, which is harmful to life. Thus, living organisms can exist in the troposphere and in the lower stratosphere. In the hydrosphere of the Earth's crust, organisms penetrate to all depths of the World Ocean - up to 10-11 km.[6] Life in the lithosphere occurs at a depth of 3.5-7.5 km, which is due to the internal temperature of the earth and the penetration of liquid water. The crucial difference between living matter and inert matter is as follows - Changes and processes occur faster in living matter than in inert matter. Therefore, geological time is used to describe the concepts of living matter, historical and inert bodies. For comparison, we note that the second period of geological time corresponds to a historical period of about one hundred thousand years. - during geological time, the power of living matter and its influence on inert matter in the biosphere increases. As VIVernadsky notes, this effect is first of all manifested "in a continuous biogenic flow by the atom from living matter to the inert matter of the biosphere and vice versa." During geological time, qualitative changes occur in organisms only in living matter. The process and

mechanisms of these changes were first described in the theory of the origin of species by Ch. Explained by Darwin's Natural Selection (1859); living organisms change depending on the changes in the environment, adapt to it, and it is the gradual accumulation of such changes that serves as the source of evolution. The process of continuous evolution, along with the emergence of new types of organisms, affects the entire biosphere, including natural biocosmic bodies. The fact that the soils and rivers of the Devonian were completely different from those of the Tertiary and especially of our time confirms this. In this way, the evolution of species gradually spread and spread throughout the biosphere.

VIVernadsky's biosphere theory . According to modern concepts, the biosphere is the earth's crust, which contains the entire collection of living organisms and a part of the planetary substance that is continuously exchanged with these organisms.

These ideas are based on the teachings of VIVernadsky (1863-1945) about the biosphere, which is the greatest of generalizations in the field of natural science. XX century His teaching in its full growth and importance appeared only in the second half of the century. This was helped by the development of global ecology, which is the main concept of ecology and, first of all, the biosphere. Vernadsky's doctrine of the biosphere is a holistic fundamental doctrine closely related to the most important problems of the preservation and development of life on Earth, which is self-regulating the planet in the past, present and future. represents a completely new approach to learning as an evolving system [7]. According to VIVernadsky's ideas , the biosphere includes living substances formed by a collection of organisms ; biogenic matter formed during the vital activity of organisms (atmospheric gases, coal, oil, peat, limestone, etc.); inert substance formed without the participation of living organisms (igneous rocks); biocosal substance, which is a joint result of vital activity of organisms and non-biological processes (soil); as well as radioactive substance, cosmic origin (meteorites, etc.) and scattered atoms. All these seven types of substances are geologically related. Living matter is a crucial part of the biosphere, so it can be argued that it can only exist and develop within the framework of an integrated biosphere system. According to VIVernadsky, living organisms are a function of the biosphere and are closely related to it materially and energetically, a very large geological force that defines it. "Living matter" thus represents a clear, precise and complete concept covering the objects of study of biology and biogeochemistry. It is very simple, clear and does not lead to misunderstanding. In science, we study only the living organism and its totality. Scientifically the same concept of life. Living matter, like the biosphere, has its own

special organizational structure and can be considered as a naturally expressed function of the biosphere. The earth's crust, the biosphere, covers the entire globe and has sharply separated dimensions, which is largely due to the presence of living matter in it - it is filled with it. Between its inanimate part, its natural bodies, and the living matter that inhabits it, there is a constant material, and a considerable exchange of energy in the motion of the atoms resulting from the living matter, which in the course of time is constantly changing and striving for equilibrium. It permeates the entire biosphere, and the biogenic flow of these atoms largely creates it. In the biogenic flow of these atoms and the energy associated with it, the value of living matter appears sharply planetary, cosmic. For the biosphere, it is simply the earth's crust, where cosmic energy enters, cosmic radiation, especially solar radiation, supports dynamic balance, organization: the biosphere is a living substance. Living matter pervades, creates and scales the entire biosphere, but it is a small part of it in terms of weight and volume. Inert, non-living matter predominates sharply; the volume is controlled by large rare gases, heavy rocks and, to a lesser extent, the liquid seawater of the World Ocean. The concentration of the largest living matter in individual cases and insignificant masses is tens of percent of this biospheric substance, and on average it is two-thirds of a percent by weight. But geologically, it is the greatest force in the biosphere, determining all the processes that take place in it, and generating enormous free energy, the main geologically manifested force in the biosphere, which is currently unquantifiable, but probably surpasses all other geological formations. Natural bodies of the biosphere are not only living organisms, but living substances, but the main mass of biosphere matter is lifeless, inert bodies, for example, atmospheric gases, rocks, chemical elements, atoms, quartz, serpentine, etc. In addition to the living and immobile natural bodies in the biosphere, various natural bodies, such as their regular structures, soil, water, surface water, bodies that live together at the same time, forming complex permanent inert living structures, also play a major role. These complex natural bodies are called bio-natural bodies. The biosphere itself is a complex planetary biocos natural body .

Analyzing the geological history of the Earth, Vernadsky points out that there is a process of transition of the biosphere to a new state - the nososphere under the influence of a new geological force, the scientific thinking of mankind. However, in Vernadsky's works, the essence of the material nosphere as a modified biosphere is not fully and consistently interpreted. In some cases, he wrote about the nosphere in the future (which has not yet arrived), in others the present (we will enter it), and sometimes associated the formation of the nosphere with the appearance of a

rational person or the appearance of industrial production. It should be noted that when Vernadsky wrote about the geological activity of man as a mineralogist, he still did not use the concepts of "nosphere" and even "biosphere". He wrote about the emergence of the nosphere on Earth as "Scientific thought is a planetary phenomenon", but mainly from the perspective of the history of science. So what is the nosphere: a utopia or a real survival strategy? Vernadsky's works allow me to give a more fair answer to the question, because they show a number of specific conditions necessary for the emergence and existence of the nosphere. We list the following conditions:

1. Human occupation of the entire planet.
2. A sudden change in communication and exchange between countries.
3. To strengthen relations between all countries on earth, including political relations.
4. The beginning of the wide spread of the geological role of man from other geological processes taking place in the biosphere.
5. Expanding the boundaries of the biosphere and the space path.
6. Discovery of new sources of energy.
7. Equality of people of all races and religions.
8. The growing role of the public in solving foreign and domestic policy issues.
9. Freedom of scientific thought and scientific research from the influence of religious, philosophical and political structures. Creation of favorable conditions for free scientific thought in the state system.
10. A well-thought-out system of public education and the improvement of the welfare of workers. Creating a real opportunity to prevent malnutrition and debilitating hunger, poverty and disease .
11. Consciously changing the original nature of the earth, which is able to satisfy all the material, aesthetic and spiritual needs of the growing population.
12. Exclusion of wars from society.

In the biosphere there is a "film of life" where the concentration of living matter is maximum. These are the upper layers of the earth's surface, soil and ocean waters. Above and below it, the amount of living matter in the Earth's biosphere decreases sharply. In his works on the biosphere, VIVernadsky paid great attention to the green living matter of plants, because only it is autotrophic, only it can absorb the energy of the Sun's radiation and use it to create primary organic compounds. VIVernadsky, considering the size and energy coefficients of different groups of plants, concluded that "the green expanses of the ocean are the main transformers of the solar energy of our planet."

Most of the energy of "living matter" goes into the formation of new vadose minerals unknown in the biosphere, and some is buried in the form of organic matter, eventually forming deposits of brown and hard coal, oil. shale, oil and gas. "We are here," VI Vernadsky writes, "we are dealing with a new process - the slow penetration of solar radiation energy that has reached the Earth's surface into the planet." In this way, "living matter" changes the biosphere and the earth's crust. It constantly leaves in it some of the chemical elements that have passed through it, forming unknown large thicknesses, in addition to which vadose minerals or the inert matter of the biosphere penetrates with the finest dust of its remains.

VI Vernadsky believed that the earth's crust is mainly the remnants of previous biospheres, and even its granite-gneiss layer was formed as a result of metamorphism and remelting of rocks that once appeared under the influence of living matter. He considered only basalts and other basic igneous rocks to be deep, the genesis of which is not related to the biosphere.

Much attention is paid to the forms of existence of various chemical elements in the biosphere, the division of the "living substance" of the biosphere into auto-hetero and mycotrophic ones according to the sources of nutrition of organisms, and the radiation of the stability field. life or limits of life, characteristics of hydrosphere and terrestrial life, geochemical cycles of condensed life, and living films of the hydrosphere [8].

It was the geological and cosmic perspectives of considering the role of living matter on the planet that led VI Vernadsky to the conclusion that the biosphere is very thick (several kilometers) and its composition is not homogeneous.

The biosphere is an organized, distinct shell of the Earth's crust that is associated with life. The boundaries of the biosphere are determined primarily by the sphere of existence of life. From these definitions, several specific concepts emerge that reveal the nature of the biosphere.

The biosphere is not one of the Earth's existing shells, such as the lithosphere, hydrosphere, and atmosphere. VI Vernadsky shows its main difference very clearly - it is an organized shell. To understand the essence of the biosphere, it is necessary to understand how and by whom it is organized, how the biosphere is organized. The biosphere has certain boundaries; that is, some finite dimension into which it can be isolated and studied scientifically. Therefore, after determining the main driving force of the development of the biosphere - living matter, it is necessary to establish spatial and temporal restrictions (boundaries) on the activity of living matter. The boundaries of the biosphere are related to the sphere of living things. But any area can be saved and preserved only when certain physical or chemical

indicators, indicators of its condition, are preserved. This means that some necessary and sufficient parameters must be established for the physical preservation of the biosphere and the "spheres of life" within the biosphere itself.

The existence of the biosphere for billions of years, the organization is created and maintained by the activity of living matter - the sum of all living organisms. The form of activity of the living, its biogeochemical work in the biosphere is the implementation of irreversible and open circulation of matter and energy flows between the main components of the biosphere integrity: rocks, natural waters, gases, soils, plants. Animals, microorganisms. This continuous process of circular movement is one of the foundations of the doctrine of the biosphere and is called biochemical cycling. The study of biochemical cycles as non-closed cycles helps to go deeper into the essence of the processes of the organization of the biosphere shell. Each subsequent state of the biosphere does not repeat the previous one. Participation in migration cycles leads to continuous renewal of the biosphere, contributes to its progressive evolutionary development, the complexity of living matter, and the increase in the diversity of living organisms.

VI Vernadsky connects the issue of the boundaries of the biosphere with the preservation of the boundaries of life. Ideas about them literally undergo fundamental changes with each new day of scientific progress. Even yesterday we were convinced that a boiling point of 100 C is impossible for the life of any living thing. Today, all the new discoveries of the world of thermophilic organisms found in volcanic vents, geysers and underwater changes are impressive C. There is information about the ability of bacteria to pass absolute zero (-273 C) temperatures.

The plasticity of life is great, but still its limits exist objectively, which determine the limits of the development of the biosphere, its structure and functions. The upper limit of the biosphere covers the entire troposphere and is limited by the ozone layer (23-25 km), which protects all life from the harmful effects of ultraviolet radiation as a kind of screen. The lower border is deeply indented; the biosphere includes the entire hydrosphere of land and the World Ocean, on the continents it enters the earth's crust at an average depth of 16 km. Here it is combined with the field of "former biospheres" - so VI Vernadsky called the preserved biosphere remnants of past geological periods. It is an accumulation of limestone, coal, oil shale, residual rocks [9].

Past biospheres are documented evidence of the geologic eternal development of the biosphere. In the great geological cycle of the movement of matter, the fossil remains of past biospheres come to the surface, are destroyed, are captured by

living organisms in new cycles of biogenic circulation, and then leave it again and fall into the deep horizons. the earth's crust, they undergo metamorphosis, remelt and store solar energy. As long as this biosphere exists, it will last for billions of years.

The age of the biosphere is approaching the geological age of the Earth as the solar system plans.

Space and time is moving of matter two main form - V. _ I. _ Vernadsky in his works strategic purpose , his whole of natural philosophy some kind of " super task was " . Around of reality to the structure deep come in to go and his each one aspect see _ _ exit wide historical illumination a naturalist reality in concepts completely _ _ expressed of reality fundamental features to look for take would not come

Time and space do not meet separately, they are inseparable. We do not know a single phenomenon that does not occupy a part of space and a part of time. Only for logical convenience we represent space and time separately, only our mind is used to try to solve any problem. Indeed, neither space nor time are separate, and we know no place except in our imagination. What are these integral parts - which, of course, only exist - this is matter that we divide into two basic coordinates: space and time. As soon as the naturalist asks himself how space and time are manifested in the individual levels of the organization of moving matter, he cannot do without answering the question: do their specific properties change in these specific forms or remain stable will it stay As you know, two answers can be given here, each of them is related to a certain historical tradition. The first of them originates from Newton, in whose theory space and time are absolute and independent of the movement of material formations. Space is an infinite capacity of objects, and time is a kind of unified world clock, against the background of which events of all scales exist and take place. From this point of view, the biosphere and life, despite representing a well-defined level of matter, lose all quality, their individuality is ignored and they dissolve like vanishing smallness. absolute society. According to the second tradition, its origin lies in the natural philosophy of Leibniz, space and time are inseparable attributes of matter. It makes no sense to claim the existence of the cosmos without the bodies of nature and about the time before the bodies appeared. Space is the arrangement of material formations, and time is the order of following them.

Vernadsky space and time nature about studies mother that's it second views to the system suitable will come In his works, the biological level of matter movement acquires its own spatio-temporal precision. According to him, time

begins its record from the moment the biosphere was created. "We are talking about historical, geological, cosmic, etc. times. It is convenient to distinguish the biological time in which life events are manifested.

This biological time one half past two billion per year right _ _ _ it comes _ time inside we On the ground biological processes existence from the Archaeozoic since we know

Now of the biosphere lifetime almost of the planet space the body as to his age correct _ _ _ _ came (about 4.5 billion year). This confirms Vernadsky's prediction about the geological eternity of the biosphere. And accordingly, a deeper layer of his thoughts about biological time was revealed: based on the general methodological approach to defining space and time, we can say that there is no time indicator before the emergence of the biosphere, because there must be biological time. is the main defining continuum in the biosphere. This implies a logical conclusion that contradicts the Newtonian tradition: not life exists against the background of the space and time of the vast universe, but the universe - life against the background of time. In other words, that habitual, self-evident idea, which has become the invisible air of science and everyday knowledge, according to which life has already passed at a certain time appeared, this idea is deeply revised by Vernadsky. Time, as we know it, flowing within us as beings of irreversible unidirectional, progressive evolution, and partly belonging to the biosphere, is real and true, not to be confused with the duration of many inanimate processes. raised to the level of time.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, VIVernadsky's approach to the study of all natural phenomena in the region of biosphere, living organisms may be correct . However, the issue of the continuous transition of the biosphere to a new state of the nosphere is a philosophical question, and therefore it cannot be answered firmly. The study of the biosphere is becoming an increasingly important and urgent task. This is due to the ever-increasing complexity of human impact on the environment. After all, we should be able to foresee all the consequences of influencing our nature. The possibility and accuracy of such predictions depends on the depth of our knowledge about the structure and activity of the biosphere, as well as its various departments and components.

8. It is very important to have an idea about the role of living organisms - the main driving force in the biosphere. of the biosphere destiny not only all experts , from the specialty exactly _ _ look , maybe almost each one of us to worry that puts problem _ It should be remembered that the creation of the biosphere is

the task of today. Its solution lies in the unification of the efforts of all mankind, the adoption of new values of cooperation and the interdependence of all peoples of the world. In our country, the ideas of the biosphere doctrine are inextricably linked with the revolutionary reconstruction of the socialist society.

9. Democracy, democratic principles of public life, revival of culture, science and people's life, radical revision of the departmental approach to nature management, etc. Vernadsky's ideas were far ahead of his time. This fully applies to the doctrine of the biosphere and its transition to the nososphere. Only now, in the context of the sharp aggravation of the global problems of our time, Vernadsky's prophetic words about the need to think and act in terms of the planet - the biosphere - have become clear. Only now, the illusions of technocratism, the conquest of nature are being broken, and the vital unity of the biosphere and humanity is being revealed. The destiny of our planet and the destiny of mankind is the only destiny. Vernadsky nosphere stage formation a lot of factors effect with links : biosphere and of humanity unity of humanity unity , man of activity planetary nature and his geological processes with compatibility , human of communication democratic forms development and planet peoples between to peace aspiration , eg not seen bloom (" burst "). and technology . This events summary of the biosphere next evolution humanity development with organic garden lip , Vernadsky and nosphere concept entered

It should be remembered that the creation of the nosphere is the task of today. Its solution lies in the unification of the efforts of all mankind, the adoption of new values of cooperation and the interdependence of all peoples of the world. Democracy, democratic principles of social life, revival of culture, science and people's life, radical revision of the departmental approach to environmental management, etc. - these are the components of the nosphere. That's why for to the future aspiration nosphere of education to himself special feature become him modern in the circumstances each bilaterally development need

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